

An Introduction to The Split-Complex Symbolic 2-Plithogenic Numbers

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Abstract:

The objective of this paper is to combine split-complex numbers with symbolic 2-plithogenic numbers in one algebraic structure called split-complex symbolic 2-plithogenic real numbers.

Also, many elementary properties of the suggested system will be handled such as Invertibility and idempotency by many related theorems and examples.

Keywords: Split-complex, symbolic 2-plithogenic number, invertible, idempotent.

Introduction and basic concepts

Split-complex numbers are considered as a generalization of real numbers, where they are defined as follows:

$$S = \{a + bJ; J^2 = 1, a, b \in R\} \quad [1].$$

Split-complex numbers together make a commutative ring with many interesting properties [2-4, 24].

Addition on S is defined as follows:

$$(t_0 + t_1J) + (k_0 + k_1J) = (t_0 + k_0) + J(t_1 + k_1).$$

Multiplication on S is defined as follows:

$$(t_0 + t_1J) \times (k_0 + k_1J) = (t_0k_0 + t_1k_1) + J(t_0k_1 + t_1k_0).$$

In [5], Smarandache presented symbolic n-plithogenic sets, then they were used in generalizing many famous algebraic structures such as ring, matrices, and other structures [6-9,15-18].

We refer to many similar numerical systems that generalize real numbers, such as neutrosophic, refined neutrosophic numbers and weak fuzzy numbers [10-14,19-23].

Through this paper, we use symbolic 2-plithogenic real numbers with split-complex numbers to build a new generalization of real numbers, and we present some of its elementary algebraic properties.

Definition.

The symbolic 2-plithogenic ring of real numbers is defined as follows:

$$2 - SP_R = \{t_0 + t_1P_1 + t_2P_2; t_i \in R, P_1 \times P_2 = P_2 \times P_1 = P_2, P_1^2 = P_2^2 = P_2\}.$$

The addition operation on $2 - SP_R$ is defined as follows:

$$(t_0 + t_1P_1 + t_2P_2) + (t'_0 + t'_1P_1 + t'_2P_2) = (t_0 + t'_0) + (t_1 + t'_1)P_1 + (t_2 + t'_2)P_2$$

The multiplication on $2 - SP_R$ is defined as follows:

$$(t_0 + t_1P_1 + t_2P_2)(t'_0 + t'_1P_1 + t'_2P_2) = t_0t'_0 + (t_0t'_1 + t_1t'_0 + t_1t'_1)P_1 + (t_0t'_2 + t_1t'_2 + t_2t'_2 + t_2t'_0 + t_2t'_1)P_2.$$

Main concepts.

Definition.

The set of split-complex symbolic 2-plithogenic numbers is defined as follows:

$$2 - SP_S = \{(x_0 + x_1P_1 + x_2P_2) + J(y_0 + y_1P_1 + y_2P_2); x_i, y_i \in R, J^2 = 1\}.$$

Definition.

Addition on $2 - SP_S$ is defined as follows:

$$[(x_0 + x_1P_1 + x_2P_2) + J(y_0 + y_1P_1 + y_2P_2)] + [(z_0 + z_1P_1 + z_2P_2) + J(t_0 + t_1P_1 + t_2P_2)] = [(x_0 + z_0) + (x_1 + z_1)P_1 + (x_2 + z_2)P_2] + J[(y_0 + t_0) + (y_1 + t_1)P_1 + (y_2 + t_2)P_2].$$

Multiplication on $2 - SP_S$ is defined as follows

For $X = (x_0 + x_1P_1 + x_2P_2) + J(x'_0 + x'_1P_1 + x'_2P_2), Y = (y_0 + y_1P_1 + y_2P_2) + J(y'_0 + y'_1P_1 + y'_2P_2),$

then

$$X.Y = (x_0 + x_1P_1 + x_2P_2)(y_0 + y_1P_1 + y_2P_2) + (x'_0 + x'_1P_1 + x'_2P_2)(y'_0 + y'_1P_1 + y'_2P_2) + J[(x_0 + x_1P_1 + x_2P_2)(y'_0 + y'_1P_1 + y'_2P_2) + (x'_0 + x'_1P_1 + x'_2P_2)(y_0 + y_1P_1 + y_2P_2)].$$

Example.

Consider $X = (P_1 + P_2) + J(1 + 3P_2), Y = (1 - P_2) + J(2 - P_1),$ then:

$$X + Y = (1 + P_1) + J(3 - P_1 + 3P_2)$$

$$X.Y = (P_1 + P_2)(1 - P_2) + (1 + 3P_2)(2 - P_1) + J[(P_1 + P_2)(2 - P_1) + (1 + 3P_2)(1 - P_2)] = P_1 - P_2 + P_2 - P_2 + 2 - P_1 + 6P_2 - 3P_2 + J[2P_1 - P_1 + 2P_2 - P_2 + 1 - P_2 + 3P_2 - 3P_2] = (2 + 2P_2) + J(1 + P_1).$$

Remark.

$(2 - SP_S, +, \cdot)$ Is a commutative ring.

Invertibility.

Theorem.

Let $X = (m_0 + m_1P_1 + m_2P_2) + J(n_0 + n_1P_1 + n_2P_2) \in 2 - SP_S,$ then X is invertible if and only if:

$$\begin{cases} (m_0 - n_0) + (m_1 - n_1)P_1 + (m_2 - n_2)P_2 \\ ((m_0 + n_0) + (m_1 + n_1)P_1 + (m_2 + n_2)P_2 \end{cases}$$

Are invertible in $2 - SP_R.$

On the other hand:

$$\begin{aligned} X^{-1} = \frac{1}{X} = \frac{m_0}{m_0^2 - n_0^2} + P_1 \left[\frac{m_0 + m_1}{(m_0 + m_1)^2 - (n_0 + n_1)^2} - \frac{m_0}{m_0^2 - n_0^2} \right] \\ + P_2 \left[\frac{m_0 + m_1 + m_2}{(m_0 + m_1 + m_2)^2 - (n_0 + n_1 + n_2)^2} - \frac{m_0 + m_1}{(m_0 + m_1)^2 - (n_0 + n_1)^2} \right] \\ - J \left[\frac{n_0}{m_0^2 - n_0^2} + P_1 \left[\frac{n_0 + n_1}{(m_0 + m_1)^2 - (n_0 + n_1)^2} - \frac{n_0}{m_0^2 - n_0^2} \right] \right. \\ \left. + P_2 \left[\frac{n_0 + n_1 + n_2}{(m_0 + m_1 + m_2)^2 - (n_0 + n_1 + n_2)^2} - \frac{n_0 + n_1}{(m_0 + m_1)^2 - (n_0 + n_1)^2} \right] \right] \end{aligned}$$

Proof.

Put $X = M + NJ; M = m_0 + m_1P_1 + m_2P_2, N = n_0 + n_1P_1 + n_2P_2$.

According to [2], X is invertible if and only if $M + N, M - N$ are invertible, hence:

$$\begin{cases} (m_0 - n_0) + (m_1 - n_1)P_1 + (m_2 - n_2)P_2 \\ (m_0 + n_0) + (m_1 + n_1)P_1 + (m_2 + n_2)P_2 \end{cases}$$

Are invertible in $2 - SP_R$.

$$\text{Also, } X^{-1} = \frac{1}{X} = \frac{M-NJ}{M^2-N^2} = \frac{M}{M^2-N^2} - J \frac{N}{M^2-N^2}.$$

According to [], we can write:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{M}{M^2 - N^2} &= M \cdot \frac{1}{M^2 - N^2} \\ &= (m_0 + m_1P_1 + m_2P_2) \left[\frac{1}{m_0^2 - n_0^2} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + P_1 \left[\frac{1}{(m_0 + m_1)^2 - (n_0 + n_1)^2} - \frac{1}{m_0^2 - n_0^2} \right] \right. \\ &\quad \left. + P_2 \left[\frac{1}{(m_0 + m_1 + m_2)^2 - (n_0 + n_1 + n_2)^2} - \frac{1}{(m_0 + m_1)^2 - (n_0 + n_1)^2} \right] \right] \\ &= \frac{m_0}{m_0^2 - n_0^2} + P_1 \left[\frac{m_0 + m_1}{(m_0 + m_1)^2 - (n_0 + n_1)^2} - \frac{m_0}{m_0^2 - n_0^2} \right] \\ &\quad + P_2 \left[\frac{m_0 + m_1 + m_2}{(m_0 + m_1 + m_2)^2 - (n_0 + n_1 + n_2)^2} - \frac{m_0 + m_1}{(m_0 + m_1)^2 - (n_0 + n_1)^2} \right] \end{aligned}$$

By a similar argument, we get:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{N}{M^2 - N^2} &= \frac{n_0}{m_0^2 - n_0^2} + P_1 \left[\frac{n_0 + n_1}{(m_0 + m_1)^2 - (n_0 + n_1)^2} - \frac{n_0}{m_0^2 - n_0^2} \right] \\ &\quad + P_2 \left[\frac{n_0 + n_1 + n_2}{(m_0 + m_1 + m_2)^2 - (n_0 + n_1 + n_2)^2} - \frac{n_0 + n_1}{(m_0 + m_1)^2 - (n_0 + n_1)^2} \right] \end{aligned}$$

Thus, the proof holds.

Example.

Take $X = (1 + P_1) + J(2 - P_1 + 2P_2) \in 2 - SP_S$, then:

$$M = 1 + P_1, N = 2 - P_1 + 2P_2, M + N = 3 + P_2, M - N = -1 + 2P_1 - 2P_2$$

$M + N, M - N$ are invertible in $2 - SP_R$.

$$\begin{aligned} X^{-1} &= \frac{1}{-3} + P_1 \left(\frac{2}{3} - \frac{1}{-3} \right) + P_2 \left(\frac{2}{-5} - \frac{2}{3} \right) - J \left[\frac{2}{-3} + P_1 \left(\frac{1}{3} - \frac{1}{-3} \right) + P_2 \left(\frac{3}{-5} - \frac{1}{3} \right) \right] \\ &= \frac{-1}{3} + P_1 + P_2 \left(-\frac{16}{15} \right) + J \left(\frac{2}{3} - \frac{2}{3}P_1 + \frac{4}{15}P_2 \right) \end{aligned}$$

Idempotency.

Let $X = M + NJ$; $M = m_0 + m_1P_1 + m_2P_2$, $N = n_0 + n_1P_1 + n_2P_2 \in 2 - SP_R$.

then X is called idempotent if and only if $X^2 = X$.

First, we compute X^2 :

$$X^2 = M^2 + N^2 + 2MNJ = m_0^2 + n_0^2 + P_1[(m_0 + m_1)^2 + (n_0 + n_1)^2 - m_0^2 - n_0^2] + P_2[(m_0 + m_1 + m_2)^2 + (n_0 + n_1 + n_2)^2 - (m_0 + m_1)^2 - (n_0 + n_1)^2].$$

The equation $X^2 = X$ is equivalent to:

$$\begin{cases} m_0^2 + n_0^2 = m_0 & (1) \\ (m_0 + m_1)^2 + (n_0 + n_1)^2 = m_0 + m_1 & (2) \\ (m_0 + m_1 + m_2)^2 + (n_0 + n_1 + n_2)^2 = m_0 + m_1 + m_2 & (3) \\ N(2M - 1) = 0 & (4) \end{cases}$$

Equation (4) is equivalent to:

$$\begin{cases} n_0(2m_0 - 1) = 0 & (5) \\ (n_0 + n_1)(2m_0 + 2m_1 - 1) = 0 & (6) \\ (n_0 + n_1 + n_2)(2m_0 + 2m_1 + 2m_2 - 1) = 0 & (7) \end{cases}$$

Equation (5) implies that $n_0 = 0$ or $m_0 = \frac{1}{2}$

If $n_0 \neq 0, m_0 \neq \frac{1}{2}$, then from (1), we get $m_1 = 0$ or $m_0 = 1$.

If $n_0 \neq 0, m_0 = \frac{1}{2}$, then from (1), we get $n_0 = \frac{1}{2}$ or $n_0 = -\frac{1}{2}$.

If $n_0 = 0, m_0 = \frac{1}{2}$, we get a contradiction:

Equation (6) implies that $n_0 + n_1 = 0$ or $m_0 + m_1 = \frac{1}{2}$

If $n_0 + n_1 \neq 0, m_0 + m_1 \neq \frac{1}{2}$, then $m_0 + m_1 = 0$ or $m_0 + m_1 = 1$.

If $n_0 + n_1 \neq 0, m_0 + m_1 = \frac{1}{2}$, then $n_0 + n_1 = \frac{1}{2}$ or $n_0 + n_1 = -\frac{1}{2}$.

If $n_0 + n_1 = 0, m_0 + m_1 = \frac{1}{2}$, we get a contradiction:

Equation (7) implies that $n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = 0$ or $m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = \frac{1}{2}$

If $n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = 0, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 \neq \frac{1}{2}$, then $m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = 0$ or $m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = 1$.

If $n_0 + n_1 + n_2 \neq 0, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = \frac{1}{2}$, then $n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = \frac{1}{2}$ or $n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = -\frac{1}{2}$.

If $n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = 0, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = \frac{1}{2}$, we get a contradiction:

The possible cases are:

Case 1.

$n_0 = 0, m_0 = 0, n_0 + n_1 = 0, m_0 + m_1 = 0, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = 0, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = 0$, then
 $X = 0$.

Case 2.

$n_0 = 0, m_0 = 0, n_0 + n_1 = 0, m_0 + m_1 = 1, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = 0, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = 0$, then
 $X = P_1 - P_2$.

Case 3.

$n_0 = 0, m_0 = 0, n_0 + n_1 = 0, m_0 + m_1 = 1, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = 0, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = 1$, then
 $X = P_1$.

Case 4.

$n_0 = 0, m_0 = 0, n_0 + n_1 = 0, m_0 + m_1 = 0, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = 0, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = 1$, then
 $X = P_2$.

Case 5.

$n_0 = 0, m_0 = 1, n_0 + n_1 = 0, m_0 + m_1 = 0, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = 0, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = 0$, then
 $X = 1 - P_1$.

Case 6.

$n_0 = 0, m_0 = 1, n_0 + n_1 = 0, m_0 + m_1 = 0, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = 0, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = 1$, then
 $X = 1 - P_1 + P_2$.

Case 7.

$n_0 = 0, m_0 = 1, n_0 + n_1 = 0, m_0 + m_1 = 1, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = 0, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = 0$, then
 $X = 1 - P_2$.

Case 8.

$n_0 = 0, m_0 = 1, n_0 + n_1 = 0, m_0 + m_1 = 1, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = 0, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = 1$, then
 $X = 1$

Case 9.

$n_0 = 0, m_0 = 0, n_0 + n_1 = \frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = 0, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = 0$, then
 $X = \left(\frac{1}{2}P_1 - \frac{1}{2}P_2\right) + J\left(\frac{1}{2}P_1 - \frac{1}{2}P_2\right)$.

Case 10.

$$n_0 = 0, m_0 = 0, n_0 + n_1 = -\frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = 0, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = 0,$$

$$\text{then } X = \left(\frac{1}{2}P_1 - \frac{1}{2}P_2\right) + J\left(-\frac{1}{2}P_1 + \frac{1}{2}P_2\right).$$

Case 11.

$$n_0 = 0, m_0 = 0, n_0 + n_1 = \frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = 0, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = 1, \text{ then}$$

$$X = \left(\frac{1}{2}P_1 + \frac{1}{2}P_2\right) + J\left(\frac{1}{2}P_1 - \frac{1}{2}P_2\right).$$

Case 12.

$$n_0 = 0, m_0 = 0, n_0 + n_1 = -\frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = 0, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = 1,$$

$$\text{then } X = \left(\frac{1}{2}P_1 + \frac{1}{2}P_2\right) + J\left(-\frac{1}{2}P_1 + \frac{1}{2}P_2\right).$$

Case 13.

$$n_0 = 0, m_0 = 1, n_0 + n_1 = \frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = 0, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = 0, \text{ then}$$

$$X = \left(1 - \frac{1}{2}P_1 - \frac{1}{2}P_2\right) + J\left(\frac{1}{2}P_1 - \frac{1}{2}P_2\right).$$

Case 14.

$$n_0 = 0, m_0 = 1, n_0 + n_1 = -\frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = 0, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = 1,$$

$$\text{then } X = \left(1 - \frac{1}{2}P_1 + \frac{1}{2}P_2\right) + J\left(-\frac{1}{2}P_1 + \frac{1}{2}P_2\right).$$

Case 15.

$$n_0 = 0, m_0 = 1, n_0 + n_1 = \frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = 0, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = 1, \text{ then}$$

$$X = \left(1 - \frac{1}{2}P_1 + \frac{1}{2}P_2\right) + J\left(\frac{1}{2}P_1 - \frac{1}{2}P_2\right).$$

Case 16.

$$n_0 = 0, m_0 = 1, n_0 + n_1 = -\frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = 0, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = 0,$$

$$\text{then } X = \left(1 - \frac{1}{2}P_1 - \frac{1}{2}P_2\right) + J\left(-\frac{1}{2}P_1 + \frac{1}{2}P_2\right).$$

Case 17.

$$n_0 = 0, m_0 = 0, n_0 + n_1 = 0, m_0 + m_1 = 0, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = \frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = \frac{1}{2}, \text{ then}$$

$$X = \frac{1}{2}P_2 + J\left(\frac{1}{2}P_2\right).$$

Case 18.

$$n_0 = 0, m_0 = 0, n_0 + n_1 = 0, m_0 + m_1 = 0, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = -\frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = \frac{1}{2}$$

$$\text{then } X = \frac{1}{2}P_2 - \frac{1}{2}P_2J.$$

Case 19.

$$n_0 = 0, m_0 = 0, n_0 + n_1 = 0, m_0 + m_1 = 1, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = \frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = \frac{1}{2}, \text{ then}$$

$$X = P_1 - \frac{1}{2}P_2 + \frac{1}{2}P_2J.$$

Case 20.

$$n_0 = 0, m_0 = 0, n_0 + n_1 = 0, m_0 + m_1 = 1, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = -\frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = \frac{1}{2}$$

$$\text{then } X = P_1 - \frac{1}{2}P_2 - \frac{1}{2}P_2J.$$

Case 21.

$$n_0 = 0, m_0 = 1, n_0 + n_1 = 0, m_0 + m_1 = 0, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = \frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = \frac{1}{2}, \text{ then}$$

$$X = \left(1 - P_1 + \frac{1}{2}P_2\right) + \frac{1}{2}P_2J.$$

Case 22.

$$n_0 = 0, m_0 = 1, n_0 + n_1 = 0, m_0 + m_1 = 0, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = -\frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = \frac{1}{2}$$

$$\text{then } X = \left(1 - P_1 + \frac{1}{2}P_2\right) - \frac{1}{2}P_2J.$$

Case 23.

$$n_0 = 0, m_0 = 1, n_0 + n_1 = 0, m_0 + m_1 = 1, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = \frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = \frac{1}{2}, \text{ then}$$

$$X = \left(1 - \frac{1}{2}P_2\right) + \frac{1}{2}P_2J.$$

Case 24.

$$n_0 = 0, m_0 = 1, n_0 + n_1 = 0, m_0 + m_1 = 1, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = -\frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = \frac{1}{2}$$

$$\text{then } X = \left(1 - \frac{1}{2}P_2\right) - \frac{1}{2}P_2J.$$

Case 25.

$$n_0 = 0, m_0 = 1, n_0 + n_1 = \frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = \frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = \frac{1}{2}, \text{ then}$$

$$X = \left(\frac{1}{2}P_1\right) + \frac{1}{2}P_1J.$$

Case 26.

$$n_0 = 0, m_0 = 1, n_0 + n_1 = \frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = -\frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = \frac{1}{2},$$

$$\text{then } X = \left(\frac{1}{2}P_1\right) + \left(\frac{1}{2}P_1 - P_2\right)J.$$

Case 27.

$$n_0 = 0, m_0 = 1, n_0 + n_1 = -\frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = \frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = \frac{1}{2},$$

$$\text{then } X = \left(\frac{1}{2}P_1\right) + \left(-\frac{1}{2}P_1 + P_2\right)J.$$

Case 28.

$$n_0 = 0, m_0 = 1, n_0 + n_1 = -\frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = -\frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = \frac{1}{2},$$

$$\text{then } X = \left(\frac{1}{2}P_1\right) + \left(-\frac{1}{2}P_1\right)J.$$

Case 29.

$$n_0 = 0, m_0 = 1, n_0 + n_1 = \frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = \frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = \frac{1}{2}, \text{ then}$$

$$X = \left(1 - \frac{1}{2}P_1\right) + \left(\frac{1}{2}P_1\right)J.$$

Case 30.

$$n_0 = 0, m_0 = 1, n_0 + n_1 = \frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = -\frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = \frac{1}{2},$$

$$\text{then } X = \left(1 - \frac{1}{2}P_1\right) + \left(\frac{1}{2}P_1 - P_2\right)J.$$

Case 31.

$$n_0 = 0, m_0 = 1, n_0 + n_1 = -\frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = \frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = \frac{1}{2},$$

$$\text{then } X = \left(1 - \frac{1}{2}P_1\right) + \left(-\frac{1}{2}P_1 + P_2\right)J.$$

Case 32.

$$n_0 = 0, m_0 = 1, n_0 + n_1 = -\frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = -\frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = \frac{1}{2},$$

$$\text{then } X = \left(1 - \frac{1}{2}P_1\right) + \left(-\frac{1}{2}P_1\right)J.$$

Case 33.

$$n_0 = \frac{1}{2}, m_0 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 = 0, m_0 + m_1 = 0, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = 0, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = 0, \text{ then}$$

$$X = \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2}P_1\right) + \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2}P_1\right)J.$$

Case 34.

$n_0 = \frac{1}{2}, m_0 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 = 0, m_0 + m_1 = 0, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = 0, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = 1$, then
 $X = \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2}P_1 + P_2\right) + \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2}P_1\right)J$.

Case 35.

$n_0 = \frac{1}{2}, m_0 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 = 0, m_0 + m_1 = 1, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = 0, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = 0$, then
 $X = \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2}P_1 - P_2\right) + \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2}P_1\right)J$.

Case 36.

$n_0 = \frac{1}{2}, m_0 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 = 0, m_0 + m_1 = 1, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = 0, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = 0$, then
 $X = \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2}P_1 - P_2\right) + \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2}P_1\right)J$.

Case 37.

$n_0 = -\frac{1}{2}, m_0 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 = 0, m_0 + m_1 = 0, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = 0, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = 0$,
then $X = \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2}P_1\right) + \left(-\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2}P_1\right)J$.

Case 38.

$n_0 = -\frac{1}{2}, m_0 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 = 0, m_0 + m_1 = 0, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = 0, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = 1$,
then $X = \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2}P_1 + P_2\right) + \left(-\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2}P_1\right)J$.

Case 39.

$n_0 = -\frac{1}{2}, m_0 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 = 0, m_0 + m_1 = 1, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = 0, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = 0$,
then $X = \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2}P_1 - P_2\right) + \left(-\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2}P_1\right)J$.

Case 40.

$n_0 = -\frac{1}{2}, m_0 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 = 0, m_0 + m_1 = 1, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = 0, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = 1$,
then $X = \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2}P_1\right) + \left(-\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2}P_1\right)J$.

Case 41.

$n_0 = \frac{1}{2}, m_0 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 = 0, m_0 + m_1 = 0, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = \frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = \frac{1}{2}$, then
 $X = \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2}P_1 + \frac{1}{2}P_2\right) + \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2}P_1 + \frac{1}{2}P_2\right)J$.

Case 42.

$$n_0 = \frac{1}{2}, m_0 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 = 0, m_0 + m_1 = 0, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = -\frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = \frac{1}{2},$$

$$\text{then } X = \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2}P_1 + \frac{1}{2}P_2\right) + \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2}P_1 - \frac{1}{2}P_2\right)J.$$

Case 43.

$$n_0 = -\frac{1}{2}, m_0 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 = 0, m_0 + m_1 = 0, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = \frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = \frac{1}{2},$$

$$\text{then } X = \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2}P_1 + \frac{1}{2}P_2\right) + \left(-\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2}P_1 + \frac{1}{2}P_2\right)J.$$

Case 44.

$$n_0 = -\frac{1}{2}, m_0 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 = 0, m_0 + m_1 = 0, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = -\frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = \frac{1}{2},$$

$$\text{then } X = \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2}P_1 + \frac{1}{2}P_2\right) + \left(-\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2}P_1 - \frac{1}{2}P_2\right)J.$$

Case 45.

$$n_0 = \frac{1}{2}, m_0 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 = 0, m_0 + m_1 = 0, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = \frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = \frac{1}{2}, \text{ then}$$

$$X = \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2}P_1 - \frac{1}{2}P_2\right) + \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2}P_1 + \frac{1}{2}P_2\right)J.$$

Case 46.

$$n_0 = \frac{1}{2}, m_0 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 = 0, m_0 + m_1 = 1, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = -\frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = \frac{1}{2},$$

$$\text{then } X = \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2}P_1 - \frac{1}{2}P_2\right) + \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2}P_1 - \frac{1}{2}P_2\right)J.$$

Case 47.

$$n_0 = -\frac{1}{2}, m_0 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 = 0, m_0 + m_1 = 1, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = \frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = \frac{1}{2},$$

$$\text{then } X = \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2}P_1 - \frac{1}{2}P_2\right) + \left(-\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2}P_1 + \frac{1}{2}P_2\right)J.$$

Case 48.

$$n_0 = -\frac{1}{2}, m_0 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 = 0, m_0 + m_1 = 1, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = -\frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = \frac{1}{2},$$

$$\text{then } X = \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2}P_1 - \frac{1}{2}P_2\right) + \left(-\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2}P_1 - \frac{1}{2}P_2\right)J.$$

Case 49.

$$n_0 = \frac{1}{2}, m_0 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 = \frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = 0, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = 0, \text{ then}$$

$$X = \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2}P_2\right) + \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2}P_2\right)J.$$

Case 50.

$n_0 = \frac{1}{2}, m_0 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 = \frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = 0, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = 1$, then
 $X = \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2}P_2\right) + \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2}P_2\right)J$.

Case 51.

$n_0 = -\frac{1}{2}, m_0 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 = \frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = 0, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = 0$,
then $X = \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2}P_2\right) + \left(-\frac{1}{2} + P_1 - \frac{1}{2}P_2\right)J$.

Case 52.

$n_0 = -\frac{1}{2}, m_0 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 = \frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = 0, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = 1$,
then $X = \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2}P_2\right) + \left(-\frac{1}{2} + P_1 - \frac{1}{2}P_2\right)J$.

Case 53.

$n_0 = \frac{1}{2}, m_0 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 = -\frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = 0, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = 0$,
then $X = \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2}P_2\right) + \left(\frac{1}{2} - P_1 + \frac{1}{2}P_2\right)J$.

Case 54.

$n_0 = \frac{1}{2}, m_0 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 = -\frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = 0, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = 1$,
then $X = \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2}P_2\right) + \left(\frac{1}{2} - P_1 + \frac{1}{2}P_2\right)J$.

Case 55.

$n_0 = -\frac{1}{2}, m_0 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 = -\frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = 0, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = 0$,
then $X = \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2}P_2\right) + \left(-\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2}P_2\right)J$.

Case 56.

$n_0 = -\frac{1}{2}, m_0 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 = -\frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = 0, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = 1$,
then $X = \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2}P_2\right) + \left(-\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2}P_2\right)J$.

Case 57.

$n_0 = \frac{1}{2}, m_0 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 = \frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = \frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = \frac{1}{2}$, then
 $X = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2}J$.

Case 58.

$$n_0 = \frac{1}{2}, m_0 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 = \frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = -\frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = \frac{1}{2},$$

then $X = \frac{1}{2} + \left(\frac{1}{2} - P_2\right)J$.

Case 59.

$$n_0 = \frac{1}{2}, m_0 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 = -\frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = \frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = \frac{1}{2},$$

then $X = \frac{1}{2} + \left(\frac{1}{2} - P_1 + P_2\right)J$.

Case 60.

$$n_0 = \frac{1}{2}, m_0 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 = -\frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = -\frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = \frac{1}{2},$$

then $X = \frac{1}{2} + \left(\frac{1}{2} - P_1\right)J$.

Case 61.

$$n_0 = -\frac{1}{2}, m_0 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 = -\frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = \frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = \frac{1}{2},$$

then $X = \frac{1}{2} + \left(-\frac{1}{2} + P_1\right)J$.

Case 62.

$$n_0 = -\frac{1}{2}, m_0 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 = \frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = -\frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = \frac{1}{2},$$

then $X = \frac{1}{2} + \left(-\frac{1}{2} + P_1 - P_2\right)J$.

Case 63.

$$n_0 = -\frac{1}{2}, m_0 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 = -\frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = \frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = \frac{1}{2},$$

then $X = \frac{1}{2} + \left(-\frac{1}{2} + P_2\right)J$.

Case 64.

$$n_0 = -\frac{1}{2}, m_0 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 = -\frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 = \frac{1}{2}, n_0 + n_1 + n_2 = -\frac{1}{2}, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = \frac{1}{2},$$

then $X = \frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2}J$.

Conclusion

In this paper, we have defined for the first time the ring of split-complex symbolic 2-plithogenic numbers by combining split-complex numbers with symbolic 2-plithogenic numbers.

We have studied many elementary properties of the novel generalized system, where necessary and sufficient conditions for Invertibility and idempotency of

symbolic 2-plithogenic split-complex numbers were handled by many related theorems and valid examples.

In the future, we aim to study matrix systems and functional systems generated by the novel algebraic structure.

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Received 5/7/2023, Accepted 27/9/2023